

Between inflated expectations and inherent distrust: How publics see the role of experts in governing climate intervention technologies

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ABSTRACT

Novel technologies for removing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and proposals around solar radiation modification, known also as solar geoengineering, display key features of complex problems. These climate intervention technologies are characterized by high uncertainties, value disputes, high stakes and urgency. Such features create wicked conundrums in climate governance. Addressing questions around more effective governance of these technologies necessitates reflections on how different kinds of expertise, normative judgments and democratic decision-making (should) interact. Based on a survey (N = 22,222) and 44 focus groups (N = 323) in 22 countries, we show (i) who publics see as an expert in the field of climate intervention technologies, (ii) what roles they envision for experts in governing climate intervention technologies and (iii) how trust and distrust in scientists unfolds in the context of these novel, partly controversial, technologies. Our findings contribute to the debate regarding public preferences for experts and expertise in decision-making on complex and potentially contested issues. They offer insights for experts in the field on how to communicate and engage in public debate and policymaking as well as on which drivers of public dis-/trust to attend.

1. Introduction

Amidst escalating climate-related extreme events, the urgency to provide policymakers with insights and evidence on a wide range of potential human interventions has perhaps never been greater. As global efforts to dramatically reduce emissions and mitigate climate change remain off course (Rogelj et al., 2023; Minx et al., 2024), discussions on carbon dioxide removal (CDR) (Smith et al., 2024) and solar radiation modification (SRM) technologies (Baur et al., 2023; SAPEA, 2024; UNEP, 2023) are gaining momentum in both science and policy communities.

These technologies, sometimes collectively referred to as climate intervention technologies or climate geoengineering (Sovacool, 2021), reflect the key features of complex, post-normal problems that are characterized by high uncertainties, value disputes, high stakes and urgency (Funtowicz and Ravetz, 1993). Practices and technologies for CDR and even more so SRM come with unknowns and uncertainties regarding their efficacy (e.g. National Research Council, 2015a, 2015b; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2024).

They involve trade-offs and entail risks and side-effects that invite value disputes and add to the stakes involved (Fuss et al., 2020; Strefler et al., 2021; Psarras et al., 2017). At the same time the climate crisis to which they are expected to respond is characterized by high urgency and – at least in the case of CDR - pressing decisions about the contours and scale of their deployment (Nemet et al., 2023).

Such factors make climate intervention and geoengineering prone to wicked governance challenges and high potential for governance failures. Foundational work in public policy, governance, game theory, behavioral economics, and polycentric networks suggests that certain variables must be present to govern complex problems such as environmental pollution or climate change (Dietz et al., 2003; Ostrom 2009a; Ostrom 2009b; Poteete et al., 2010). These include: the availability of reliable information with minimal transaction costs related to its collection; open and frequent communication among stakeholders regarding costs and benefits; effective rule enforcement and provisions for forcing compliance (such as sanctions); and predictable and gradual changes to rules and enforcement when they occur. Such work also tends to highlight the importance of diverse actors, including local

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Table 1
Overview of three adjacent strands of literature combined in this paper.

Literature(s)	Key themes & concepts	Selected references
Roles of experts in decision-making, with a focus on climate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Linear models of science-policy relations vs. co-productive arrangements, transdisciplinary practices, and boundary organizations Ideal-typical roles of scientists in policymaking, differentiating e.g. differentiates between the “pure scientist”, “science arbiter”, “issue advocate”, and “honest broker” 	Maas et al. (2022); Turnhout et al. (2020); Schneider et al. (2019); Guston, (2001); Hoppe et al. (2013); Pielke (2007)
Public perceptions of experts and trust in scientists, with a focus on climate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Competence, integrity, benevolence, and openness as key ingredients of scientists’ perceived trustworthiness Correlates of public (dis-)trust in scientists, e.g. political leaning, spirituality Political advocacy and credibility of climate scientists Technocratic legitimacy in case of complex problems 	Review by Cologna et al. (2024); Rutjens et al. (2022); Beebe et al. (2019); Cologna et al. (2021); Kotcher et al. (2017); Nicolaisen (2022); Bertson (2022)
Trust in science and technology perceptions, with a focus on climate interventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trust in institutions, including scientific ones, strongly relates to public perceptions of CDR and SRM Trust is particularly crucial for novel technologies with which the public is unfamiliar 	Braun et al. (2018); Jobin and Siegrist, (2020); Klaus et al. (2020); Nawaz et al. (2023); Otto and Matzner, (2024); Pidgeon and Spence, (2017); Satterfield et al. (2023); Merk et al. (2015); Fairbrother, (2016); Cummings and Rosenthal, (2018); Fenn et al. (2023); Baum et al. (2024a); Brutschin et al. (2024); Bolsen et al. (2024); Hussain et al. (2024); Sugiyama et al. (2024); Zhang et al. (2024)

stakeholders (fishers, farmers, Indigenous groups) and citizens (Andersson and Ostrom, 2008; Ostrom 2009c; Mewhirter et al., 2018; Morrison et al., 2023). Conversely, rapid changes in technology, information failures between groups or across generations, and unchecked opportunistic or rent seeking behavior acutely corrode effective governance and complicate cooperative efforts (Ostrom, et al., 1994; Ostrom, 2000; Ostrom et al., 1999). This is also true of networks with a limited or homogenous representation of actors (Sovacool, 2011; Sovacool and Van de Graaf, 2018; Sovacool and Martiskainen, 2020). Findings from research on the public understanding of science in fields such as health, furthermore, suggest that addressing the socio-technical complexities related to experimentation and (potential) deployment of climate intervention technologies necessitates an interrogation of the hierarchy of expertise, values and interests in deciding which voices are heard, or not heard, and of political agility in continuously evolving situations (Lohse and Bschor, 2020). Underlying reflections on how different kinds of expertise, normative judgments and democratic decision-making (should) interact are reminiscent of long-standing debates in the wider field of climate change (Bäckstrand, 2004; Low et al., 2022a).

Climate intervention technologies, thus, offer an ideal case for studying public views, expectations and concerns about the role of experts in tackling complex, post-normal, issues. In this article, based on a survey (N = 22,222) and 44 focus groups (N = 323) in 22 countries, we ask “How do publics see the role of experts in governing climate intervention technologies?”. In presenting results from this mixed-methods study, we focus on (i) who publics see as an expert in the field of climate intervention technologies, (ii) what roles they envision for experts in governing climate intervention technologies and (iii) how trust (and distrust) in scientists unfolds in the context of these novel, partly controversial, technologies. Ultimately, this study contributes to opening up the debate regarding public preferences for independent experts in politics and the role of expertise in decision-making on complex and potentially contested issues. It offers insights for experts in the field on how to communicate and engage in public debate and policymaking as well as on which drivers of public dis-/trust to attend.

2. Literature review and conceptual background

In this article, we integrate and build on three adjacent bodies of literature concerning (i) conceptions of the role of scientific experts in decision-making, (ii) correlates of public trust and distrust in (climate) scientists, and (iii) the relationship between public (dis-)trust in science and perceptions of novel technologies and practices in the field of climate (see Table 1).

2.1. Roles of experts in decision-making

There is ample conceptual and empirical literature in the field of science and technology studies (STS), sociology and political science, discussing how interactions between science, policy and society are or should be organized. For one, in “linear models” science and policy appear as clearly demarcated spheres. New knowledge and scientific evidence are here assumed to directly feed into and be used in policy-making (e.g. Kowalczywska and Behagel, 2019). Such conceptions persist in public representations of science-policy interactions and are, for example, mobilized in calls for climate action in the climate movement, using slogans like “listen to the scientists” (e.g. Soßdorf and Burgi, 2022).

Concerned about knowledge-action gaps (e.g. Knutti, 2019) and acknowledging the complexity and value-laden nature of societal transformation (Fazey et al., 2017), public calls for policymakers to “listen” or “follow the sciences” are increasingly considered an insufficient strategy (Pohlmann et al., 2021). Accordingly, scholars in the field of sustainability and environment have been calling for a shift from linear conceptions of science-policy interactions to co-productive arrangements (see Bandola-Gill et al., 2023; Maas et al., 2022; Turnhout et al., 2020; van der Hel, 2016), transdisciplinary practices (Schneider et al., 2019) and the creation of boundary organizations positioned in-between scientific and policymaking spaces and translating between the two (Guston, 2001; Hoppe et al., 2013; Kirsop-Taylor and Russel, 2022). To varying degrees these approaches also emphasize the importance of including practical, experience-based or indigenous knowledge, broadly categorized – in contrast to expertise of scientists – as non-certified expertise (Collins and Evans, 2002).

Beyond these broader organizational perspectives on science-policy interactions, these literatures also include conceptions focused on individual actors, offering for example ideal-typical conceptions of the role of scientists in policymaking. Most notably, Pielke’s (2007) typology of idealized modes of engagement differentiates between the “pure scientist”, “science arbiter”, “issue advocate”, and “honest broker”.

2.2. Public perceptions of experts and trust in scientists

When it comes to the role of science and expertise in policymaking, public trust in science and expertise is a key concern. Some warn of a crisis of trust in science and expertise and speak of a post-truth era (Gundersen et al., 2022, Nichols, 2017); others note evidence at the global level that points to positive public attitudes towards scientists and experts broadly defined (Dommett and Pearce, 2019; Wellcome Trust, 2018; 2020; Eurobarometer, 2021).

Citizens’ views of and expectations towards climate scientists more

specifically have been attracting growing interest by scholars from psychology, sociology, science communication and media studies. In a recent review article on the state of trust in climate science, [Cologna et al. \(2024\)](#) identify competence, integrity, benevolence, and openness as key ingredients of scientists' perceived trustworthiness. While they find evidence for high levels of trust in climate science and scientists globally – with the highest levels reported among publics in South Asia and the lowest in East Asia and the Pacific – only a small fraction of the survey populations reviewed can be categorized as skeptical of climate science and scientists. The review also reports mixed results for individual characteristics associated with skepticism or distrust towards climate scientists. Spirituality seems to be more consistently associated with (dis)trust than religiosity, and, especially in the US, distrust tends to be particularly associated with right-wing and conservative political leanings, whereas this association is weak or absent in other contexts ([Rutjens et al., 2022](#)). Notably, concerns among the distrusting publics emerge over aspects of scientific production, such as untransparent and dubious funding sources which may bias climate scientists and their research and over their motives and motivations (e.g. [Rowland et al., 2022](#); [Sarathchandra and Haltinner, 2020](#)).

The question of whether and how political advocacy and policy engagement of climate scientists affects their credibility, and trustworthiness has received growing attention in recent years. In a survey, [Beebe et al. \(2019\)](#) find that educated non-experts do not hold strong opinions about whether climate scientists should develop policy recommendations as part of their science communication and public outreach. In their experimental study among US respondents [Kotcher et al. \(2017\)](#) show that higher levels of advocacy do not compromise the perceived credibility of climate scientists. Similarly, [Cologna et al. \(2021\)](#) find that in the eyes of German and US survey respondents policy advocacy of climate scientists does not harm their credibility and that – on the contrary – respondents in these countries even ask for greater political engagement. At the same time, qualitative data from focus groups in Denmark suggest that neither the citizens nor the climate scientists or journalists participating in the study wanted scientists to act as advocates, but only as public communicators of value-neutral science – although with a “license to display their emotions” ([Nicolaisen, 2022](#)).

The effects of other forms of engagement such as participation in civil disobedience and protest actions has hardly been studied, with some early work not finding any negative impact on credibility ([Friedman, 2024](#)). Going beyond advocacy, [Bertsou \(2022\)](#) reports based on a conjoint experiment that the higher the perceived complexity of the problem at hand, the greater the desire of publics for independent experts as decision-makers. Accordingly for tackling problems of carbon emissions and climate change publics in the seven European countries surveyed consistently express preferences for delegating decision-making powers to experts ([Bertsou, 2022](#)).

2.3. Trust in science related to technology and risk perceptions

Social science research has established that trust in science is a key element for understanding support and acceptance of novel technologies in various fields such as vaccines, stem cell research, genetic modification, nuclear power, and nanotechnology ([Siegrist, 2000](#); [Siegrist and Cvetkovich, 2000](#); [Siegrist et al., 2007](#); [Barnett et al., 2007](#); [Critchley, 2008](#); [Berube et al., 2010](#)). Beyond having a broadly positive relationship with public perceptions, [Berube et al. \(2010\)](#) revealed that such trust correlates with strengthened or reduced risk perceptions of novel technologies. According to the framework by [Earle \(2010\)](#), the importance of trust proves to be particularly crucial for novel technologies with which the public is unfamiliar though they have some knowledge of the actors and institutions involved. Trust at the science-society interface can also create risks of its own as disappointment of expectations and violations of societal trust are consequential. [Lacey et al. \(2018\)](#) argue, pointing to the example of failures in the management of Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE, also known as mad cow disease) in

the UK, that, when scientific uncertainties are glossed over and controversies insufficiently acknowledged, there is a potential for risk assessments “gone wrong”. This can lead to breaches of trust with the public, with long-lasting ramifications at the science-society interface.

Similar to other emerging technologies, there is broad evidence that trust in institutions, including scientific ones, strongly relates to public perceptions of CDR ([Braun et al., 2018](#); [Jobin and Siegrist, 2020](#); [Klaus et al., 2020](#); [Nawaz et al., 2023](#); [Otto and Matzner, 2024](#); [Pidgeon and Spence, 2017](#); [Satterfield et al., 2023](#)), SRM ([Mercer et al., 2011](#); [Merk et al., 2015](#); [Fairbrother, 2016](#); [Merk and Pönitzsch, 2017](#); [Braun et al., 2018](#); [Cummings and Rosenthal, 2018](#); [Klaus et al., 2021](#); [Fenn et al., 2023](#); [Baum et al., 2024a](#); [Bolsen et al., 2024](#); [Hussain et al., 2024](#); [Sugiyama et al., 2024](#); [Zhang et al., 2024](#)) or both ([Jobin and Siegrist, 2020](#); [Klaus et al., 2020](#); [Wenger et al., 2021](#); [Brutschin et al., 2024](#)). There is evidence that being more trustful of relevant institutions is related to greater comfort with ocean-based CDR approaches ([Nawaz et al., 2023](#); [Satterfield et al., 2023](#)). Pointing to an inverse correlation between such trust and perceptions of climate severity and urgency, the authors also observed that the perceived need to address climate risks, given a lack of faith in institutions, could prompt support for alternatives. Some studies identify trust as being among the most important correlates of (positive) perceptions of climate intervention technologies ([Merk et al., 2015](#); [Braun et al., 2018](#); [Jobin and Siegrist, 2020](#); cf. this factor was of intermediate importance in [Pidgeon and Spence, 2017](#) and [Klaus et al., 2020](#)). Supporting the interplay between the role of trust for support of unfamiliar technologies, [Jobin and Siegrist \(2020\)](#) found that trust had a significant and positive relationship with support for nine of ten CDR and SRM technologies, with the one exception of afforestation: the only one likely to be broadly familiar.

Reviewing this broad evidence makes clear that a better understanding of the formation and conditions of (dis-)trust in scientists can, thus, also deliver crucial information for fostering public engagement with novel climate intervention technologies.

3. Research methods

To examine public perceptions of expertise about climate interventions, this paper combines qualitative data from 44 focus groups ($n = 323$) with quantitative survey data from 22 countries ($n = 22,222$),¹ collected between August 2022 – January 2023. Recruitment of participants and data collection was administered by Norstat, a professional data collection company, on behalf of Aarhus University. The quantitative surveys were representative of the respective national populations (between the ages of 18 and 83) in terms of gender, geographic region, age, income, and education (with at least $N = 1000$ for each country). The composition of the focus groups was guided by diversity sampling. 44 focus groups were conducted, with one in an urban and one in a rural setting in each country.

The countries where both focus groups and surveys were implemented include 9 European countries (Austria, Germany, Italy, Norway, Poland, Sweden, Switzerland, Spain, United Kingdom), one North American country (United States), three Latin and South American countries (Brazil, Chile, Dominican Republic), three African countries (Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa), two Middle Eastern countries (Saudi Arabia, Turkey), and four countries in the Indo- and Asia-Pacific (Australia, China, India, Indonesia).

Both the focus groups and the survey were focused on gauging public attitudes towards a broad range of CDR and SRM technologies. The survey explored ten different technologies, grouped into three categories. Participants were randomly assigned to one of the following groups: SRM technologies, which included stratospheric aerosol

¹ Our original survey study included 30 countries ($n = 30,284$ respondents). In this article, we consider only those 22 countries that were also included in the focus groups, i.e. we rely on a reduced survey sample.

injection (SAI), marine cloud brightening (MCB), and space-based geo-engineering (SBG); CDR 1 technologies, encompassing afforestation and reforestation (AF), soil carbon sequestration (SCS), and marine biomass and blue carbon (MBBC); and CDR 2 technologies, covering direct air capture with carbon storage (DACCS), bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS), enhanced weathering, and biochar. Each technology was explained with brief information texts and illustrations, along with a balanced overview of its potential risks and benefits (see [Supplementary Information](#), SI, for the full survey instrument). The focus groups considered the same SRM technologies and a slightly narrower range of CDR approaches, including afforestation, reforestation, and vegetation restoration, soil carbon sequestration, including biochar, DACCS, enhanced rock weathering and BECCS.

Questions around experts formed only a small part of the overall design. The results presented here, thus, need to be interpreted in the context of a study on public perceptions of CDR/SRM, including risks, benefits and governance arrangements. Focus group participants discussed the role of experts as part of a wider reflection on actors that should or will shape governance of climate intervention technologies. When experts and scientists did not organically come up in the discussions, we prompted participants on their perceptions of scientists by asking “*What do you expect from scientists when it comes to taking decisions on technology X?*” (see [SI](#) for an overview of the discussion guide).

All focus groups were recorded, transcribed verbatim and translated to English. The empirical data were managed, coded, and analyzed with the software “MAXQDA”. We conducted thematic analysis ([Nowell et al., 2017](#)) of the focus transcripts, guided by the analytical questions outlined in [Table 2](#). The first and fourth author coded the data and adopted a “negotiated agreement” approach to establish inter-coder reliability ([Campbell et al., 2013](#)).

The last analytical dimension outlined in [Table 2](#) also takes quantitative results from the survey into account.

Trust in Science. Survey respondents were asked to indicate on a scale ranging from 1, “no trust”, to 6, “very high trust”, their level of trust in universities and scientific research institutions “*when it comes to their responsibility [and ability] to use these technologies (CDR/SRM) to limit the effects of climate change*”. We use this as our indicator of trust in scientific institutions. The same question formulation was used to ask respondents to indicate their level of trust in other institutional actors. These are: industry and corporations in the field of climate technologies, national governments and official agencies, international government

Table 2
Analytical framework guiding the qualitative coding of transcripts of the 44 focus groups.

Analytical questions	Examples of coding categories	Related conceptions in the literature
Who is seen as an expert and which kinds of expertise are considered relevant for governing climate intervention technologies? What roles should experts/scientists have in governing climate intervention technologies?	Natural sciences, engineering, social sciences; Indigenous knowledge, practical knowledge; interdisciplinarity Communicators and disseminators; advisors and consultants; decision-makers; innovators, ...	Certified vs. experienced-based knowledge (Collins and Evans, 2002) Linear vs. co-productionist models of science-policy relations (e.g. Maas et al. 2022); Pielke's (2007) typology of modes of engagement;
To what extent do publics express trust or distrust in experts/scientists in the context of climate intervention technologies and what criteria for trustworthiness do they establish?	Trust in scientists, and science; skepticism towards scientists/science; public funding; transparency; objectivity, ...	Previous empirical studies on trust in science and expertise and its determinants in the field of climate change (e.g. Cologna et al. 2024)

institutions (e.g. United Nations), and non-governmental organizations (e.g. environmental and climate groups) – the order was randomized for participants. Since in the qualitative focus groups participants discussed the role of various actors in shaping governance of climate interventions, including these in the second part of the quantitative analysis provides a richer understanding of the trusted actors in climate governance across global contexts.

Socio-demographic characteristics. To understand the individual-level correlates of trust in scientific and other (non-)governmental institutions, we included respondents’ socio-demographic characteristics. Five are categorical: gender (male and female), area of living (rural, urban, suburban), type of job (color coded as such: *grey* for resource extraction sector, *blue* for blue-collar employments, *green* for sustainability and conservation sector, *gold* for high-prestige jobs, *white* for white-collar employments), level of education and income (both coded as dichotomous variables, representing values above and below the median, computed separately for each country). Three are continuous: age, religiosity (1 = not at all religious, 6 = extremely religious) and political ideology (1 = very liberal, 7 = very conservative). Descriptive statistics of all variables are included in the [SI](#).

Analysis. For each indicator of trust, we first performed a multilevel linear regression analysis with country-level fixed effects to understand the individual characteristics associated with trust in scientific institutions. Fixed effects were employed to hold country-level variations constant. Second, for the same indicator of trust, we performed multilevel linear regression analyses with mixed effects and random slopes for all socio-demographic variables. In these models, the relationship between each of the individual level variables and the corresponding trust indicator is allowed to vary across countries. Information on political ideology is not available for China, due to sensitivity and privacy concerns. Thus, for this country we present results from separate linear regressions for each trust indicator. All analyses have been performed in R, using `lme4` for multilevel analyses and `ggplot2` for visualizations.

We have previously published some papers drawing from these data ([Brutschin et al., 2024](#); [Fritz et al., 2024](#); [Low et al., 2024a,b](#); [Sovacool et al., 2024](#); [Baum et al., 2024b](#)). However, this paper is fundamentally different from these earlier works in several key ways: here we use climate intervention technologies as an example of complex problems and focus entirely on how publics think about the role of experts, what place they envision for different types of expertise, and the correlates of trust at the science-society interface. In contrast, our earlier papers examined different facets and drivers of emerging perceptions of climate intervention technologies themselves. There is, thus, no overlap in content. Additionally, this paper integrates qualitative and quantitative data for a smaller set of countries, whereas most of our previous work was solely based on either one or the other.

4. Results

We present the results in three parts, offering insights into (i) who publics identify as experts in the field of climate intervention technologies, (ii) the roles they envision for these experts in governing climate intervention technologies and (iii) how trust - and distrust - in scientists and other relevant actors unfolds in the context of these novel technologies. The first two parts are based on the qualitative analysis of focus groups data, while the third part integrates the quantitative analysis of survey data and uses qualitative findings to deepen the analysis.

4.1. Who is seen as an expert?

In discussions on how decisions on climate intervention technologies should be taken, focus group participants mention experts and scientists as key actors for governing all of the technologies discussed. The emphasis of their role is, however, more pronounced for the SRM approaches and novel CDR technologies such as DACCS and BECCS.

Across the focus groups the predominant conception of experts in the

context of climate intervention technologies refers to natural scientists and engineers, with particularly frequent mentions of geologists, chemists, (atmospheric) physicists, biologists, agricultural and soil scientists, and aerospace engineers.

Except for a handful of mentions of economists, social scientists are glaringly absent in the reflections on relevant experts and key actors for both the SRM and the CDR approaches discussed. Focus group participants, however, do acknowledge the importance of multidimensional assessments of climate intervention technologies and identify the need for interdisciplinary collaborations – although not always named in such terms – particularly in the context of climate advisory bodies and committees in specialized, governmental or quasi-governmental agencies. A German focus group participant clearly articulates the idea of interdisciplinary collaboration:

“I would like the various scientific disciplines to work together, for there to be interdisciplinary work done, for them to build on each other, to make each other aware of certain things and to come together to a shared conclusion”. (Germany rural, discussing SAI)

Despite a dominant focus on “certified” forms of expertise (Collins and Evans, 2002), we find some mentions of non-scientific expertise, particularly the experience- and place-based knowledge of farmers and fishing communities, and to a lesser extent indigenous communities. These types of expertise are predominantly evoked regarding conventional, biogenic CDR methods such as afforestation and restoration of land and marine ecosystems, and soil carbon sequestration, as illustrated by reflections like the following from a Norwegian focus group:

“Then I also think it’s important in many parts of the country to use those who know the earth, who know the vegetation. Like indigenous people, farmers, who have carried on traditions for hundreds of years and can tell you how it was here a long time ago. There’s a lot of knowledge there.” (Norway, rural, discussion on soil carbon sequestration)”

For governing novel CDR technologies, company and industry actors are also identified as holding relevant expertise and material resources, including from the oil and gas sector, as exemplified by the following statement in the context of DACCS:

“I would like to see Equinor [Norwegian state-owned petroleum company] take the lead, because they have resources and the finances, and they also have the knowledge and the people to start in a way.” (Norway, urban, discussions on DACCS)

While non-scientific, experience-based experts are entirely absent in reflections on SAI and space mirrors, for understanding potential impacts of marine cloud brightening on marine life and ecosystems, local communities and fishermen are seen as relevant knowledge holders. A participant in the Dominican Republic, for example, shares such a reflection:

“Imagine that they [the fishermen] are also the ones who know best the animals they catch, that we have there. From the fishermen, they are the ones who are going to catch what we are going to eat.” (Dominican Republic, rural, MCB discussion)

4.2. What roles are envisioned for experts?

Participants see a wide range of roles for experts in decision-making around climate intervention technologies. In the following, we describe the three most recurring ones that are present in a plurality of focus groups.

• Knowledge providers and advisors

First, by far the most frequent narrative portrays experts as providers of evidence for decision-making as well as of practical knowledge needed for technology deployment. Participants across all countries and

for all technologies expect specialized experts to study the different technological options, assess and weigh potential benefits and risks of the respective CDR and SRM approaches and subsequently inform political decision-makers. This narrative generally reflects conceptions of a flow from knowledge produced by scientists to political decision-makers and finally to the wider public:

“I think it’s the same, scientists first to study, then the politicians, a leadership of each country, and then a divulgation for the population to raise awareness. For all the ideas [i.e. technologies].” (Brazil rural)

In this narrative we also find references to experts in roles as government advisors, and consultants with multiple analogies drawn to how advisory bodies and scientists guided governments and political leaders in tackling the Covid-19 pandemic. Overall, participants’ conceptions of the role of experts in this narrative resemble idealized modes of engagement as “science arbiter” and an “honest broker” in Pielke’s (2007) typology.

• Decision-makers

The second narrative depicts experts in the role of decision-makers on the governance of climate intervention technologies. Here participants blur the boundaries between science and policy and redistribute roles and responsibilities. In this narrative, the role of experts goes beyond providing a basis for decision-making and acting as advisors to encompass actual control over decision-making:

“Respondent 1: I think the people who need to make a decision about this are the people who can approach this business without making a profit and who have a scientific side. I guess it will be an academy. People who can definitely think in favour of the public in terms of harm or benefit in terms of their applicability and inapplicability and who will understand this issue scientifically should make this decision. Not for-profit companies. Respondent 2: All scientists can come together and think, research and decide together.” (Turkey urban)

Going beyond the role of an “issue advocate” (Pielke, 2007), scientists are here implicitly and explicitly seen as powerful actors:

“Scientists right. They have the education regarding this. They are the only people because they have that power, they got the knowledge” (Kenya, rural)

• Educators and disseminators

In the third narrative, equally mentioned for CDR and SRM approaches, experts appear in the role of knowledge disseminator and educators beyond interactions with political decision-makers. Participants repeatedly call on scientists and experts to make their knowledge accessible and understandable to public audiences through communication and dissemination efforts. Scientific institutions and educational facilities are also generically mentioned as key to knowledge dissemination, awareness raising and capacity building. The demand for such activities is particularly emphasized for conventional CDR methods where participants see a strong role for publics in supporting deployment, but also regarding climate action more generally.

Other roles identified, though not discussed in a plurality of focus groups, include experts as issue advocates that should convince decision-makers to act, as controllers of other actors, most notably, company and industry actors, and experts as innovators. In the latter case, we find imaginations of bravery, pioneering and references to “mad scientists” as illustrated by the following extract from a Polish focus group:

“[B]ecause of the climate crisis, the energy crisis that we have - you have to think ahead, you have to be a bit of a mad scientist, because if it wasn’t for them, I think we would still be stuck further in medieval age, if there

were't brave people who put the idea into practice, even 30 years ago, we didn't think that we would have smartphones." (Poland rural)

Overall, participants' conceptions go beyond the role of scientists as specialized knowledge producers, welcoming active engagement in communication, societal debates and decision-making, while calling for public funding of research to ensure independence, impartiality and objectivity.

4.3. Inflated expectations and skepticism

In the following, we show how trust - and distrust - in scientists and other relevant actors unfolds in the context of these novel technologies. To account for country specificities and socio-demographic characteristics, we integrate the quantitative analysis of survey data and use qualitative findings to deepen and contextualize analysis.

4.3.1. Signs of trust in and high expectations towards experts and scientific institutions

Complementing the qualitative accounts on how publics see the role of experts and relevant types of expertise, we employed the quantitative survey insights to explore the relationship between individual socio-demographic characteristics and our measure of trust in scientific institutions across the twenty-two countries included in our study. It is important here to keep in mind that survey respondents were asked to rate their trust in the responsibility (and ability) of scientific and other institutions to use the climate intervention technologies presented to limit the effects of climate change.

Fig. 1 presents the predicted values for each country on trust in universities and scientific research institutions, holding country-level variation constant. These have been calculated based on the corresponding fixed effects regression results included in the SI. The coefficients shown refer to the original scale of the trust variable (1–6)

Fig. 1. Predicted value of trust in universities and scientific research institutions across socio-demographic characteristics. Note: Respondents were asked to indicate on a scale ranging from 1, “no trust”, to 6, “very high trust”, their level of trust in five types of actors “when it comes to their responsibility [and ability] to use these technologies (CDR/SRM) to limit the effects of climate change”. The figure is based on a fixed effects multilevel linear regression included in the SI. X-axis based on the original scale of trust, from 1–6. Occupation color coded as such: grey for resource extraction sector, blue for blue-collar employments, green for sustainability and conservation sector, gold for high-prestige jobs, white for white-collar employments.

present a generalized picture of the association between individual socio-demographic characteristics and trust, having controlled for country-level variations.

Regarding socio-demographic characteristics, we identify a lack of association between age and trust, while being male is associated with more trust in universities compared to being a woman. Compared to living in a big city, those in any other area express less trust in universities, especially those in rural areas.

Regarding one's type of occupation, an interesting pattern emerges. Respondents employed in high prestige, and white- or blue-collar jobs seem to be homogeneous in their moderate trust. The biggest discrepancy becomes apparent between those employed in the "green" sector (e.g. renewable energy, environment and conservation) and those employed in resource extraction, fossil fuels or mining (*grey*), with the former being more trusting in scientific institutions than the latter. This disparity is less accentuated when it comes to trust in other institutions with workers of the *grey* sector being more aligned with the others, as shown in the regression results included in the SI (table A.3).

Being religious and having a liberal ideological leaning are both positively associated with higher trust in universities and scientific institutions, i.e. more religious and liberal individuals are more trusting towards universities and scientific institutions. As shown in the regression results included in the SI (table A.3), religiosity is similarly associated with trust in other institutions, with not religious respondents being least trusting of all institutional actors considered. Political ideology instead presents different patterns according to the institution considered, with liberals reporting more trust than conservatives in international government institution and non-governmental organizations but less trust in national governments and industry (see SI, A.3).

This second part of the quantitative analysis is based on results of multilevel linear regression models with mixed effects and random slopes for all socio-demographic variables. As such, these models take into consideration that the relationship between the socio-demographics

and each indicator of trust could vary in each of the countries. Fig. 2, thus, presents the expected level of trust in universities and other institutions within each country after controlling for the effects of individual characteristics. The values for China have been calculated in separate linear regression models, included in the SI, and then included in the plot.

Overall, universities and scientific institutions appear as the most trusted actors surveyed in all countries. The second most trusted actors are NGOs, although with a few exceptions in which international government institutions have higher scores (Sweden, Norway, Nigeria and China). International government institutions present stable and moderate levels of trust across countries. Business actors are overall moderately trusted in their responsibility to use the surveyed technologies to limit the effects of climate change, although with particularly low scores in Poland, Austria and Germany. National governments emerge as the least trusted institutions, although in four countries, Saudi Arabia, India, Indonesia and especially China, they have noticeably higher trust levels compared to the rest.

Looking at the general pattern of trust scores for the five items across the countries considered, a divide can be noticed between European and non-European countries from the Global North, from the left towards the center, and countries from the Global South, on the right (Fig. 2). Those on the left end of the figure present a noticeable discrepancy between their high level of trust in scientific research institutions and the lower trust scores for other institutional actors, with national governments often being the least trusted actors. In countries on the right end of the figure the five types of trust appear more intertwined, especially in the cases of Saudi Arabia, India, Indonesia, and China. The latter represents the only case in which trust in national and international government institution is higher than in universities and research institutions, recalling previous evidence (Zhang et al., 2024). Our results suggest that when interpreting high levels of public trust in scientific experts, at least in western contexts, it is important to consider the level of trust in other

Fig. 2. Average predicted values of trust in different types of actors across countries. Note: Respondents were asked to indicate on a scale ranging from 1, "no trust", to 6, "very high trust", their level of trust in five types of actors "when it comes to their responsibility [and ability] to use these technologies (CDR/SRM) to limit the effects of climate change". The order in which participants were asked to express their trust in each of the institutions was randomized. The figure is based on mixed effects multilevel linear regressions included in the SI. Y-axis based on the original scale of trust. X-axis ordered according to the average predicted value across the five types of actors for each country.

institutions to gain a more holistic picture. These results recall existing evidence in research on technocratic attitudes which already observed a relationship between preferences for experts' lead in decision making and (lack of) trust in political institutions in European contexts (Bertsou and Pastorella, 2016).

Complementing our survey findings of high trust in scientific institutions, the reflections of focus group participants on key actors for governing climate intervention technologies also point to high expectations towards (scientific) experts, particularly regarding their capacity to minimize – or even eradicate – uncertainties surrounding potential risks of novel technologies. This became apparent from the almost unanimous calls for systemic, global, open-ended assessments of risks of climate intervention technologies, particularly the SRM proposals.

We observe a strong desire for scientists to first “prove that it works” and anticipate any side effects through experiments and assessment, as reflected in discussion in this Polish focus group:

“M: what do you expect from them then [the chemists and space scientists mentioned]? R: 100% certainty that this will not destroy our planet. This is already a very big interference in the climate zone, it is already ...” (Poland, rural, discussion on the global SRM approaches).

Participants tended to think of SRM test demonstrations as locally/regionally bounded schemes that would nevertheless allow conclusions to be drawn on global impacts – sometimes implicitly comparing such tests to local infrastructural projects in terms of scale and resources, or more explicitly to weather modification. In the case of global SRM approaches, however, these high expectations towards science and its capacity to provide certainty are likely to be inflated given the fundamental challenge that potential impacts cannot be fully understood with modeling, indoor lab experiments or even small-scale trials (Low et al., 2022b). This thus necessitates clear communication of what science can and cannot deliver in terms of assessing uncertainties and unknowns – and preventing what Lacey et al. (2018) call a “crash and burn” scenario of disappointment and negative experience with science in policymaking.

Publics' reflections on the role of experts also need to be understood in relation to their views on other actors, most importantly politicians but also industry actors. As shown by the survey results, these actors predominantly - though with important cross-country variations - meet public skepticism or distrust when it comes to their ability and responsibility to use CDR and SRM technologies, particularly in some European countries such as Austria, Germany or Poland (see Fig. 2). Indeed, in many accounts from the focus groups experts and scientists appear as those who have the greater “common good” at heart, “think in favour of the public” and are - unlike politicians - not driven by vested interests and personal gain, corroborating earlier studies finding technocratic tolerance to be associated with distrust in governments (Bertou and Pastorella, 2016). The following expressions of distrust and disappointment in politicians and corresponding preference for a strong role of scientists illustrate this relationality:

“There are some world leaders that don't believe in climate change so I don't think the decision should be up to them. It should be the scientists and that would have to go through government approval. That's just how it is. Obviously like with the COVID. Boris Johnson was advised and he delivered it to the public, it's not like it was his idea when it comes to the vaccines and everything.” (UK, urban)

“You'd need reassurance from proper people, not politicians, and [...] not vested interests, yeah proper people, you know, some trustworthy universities, proper scientists that aren't on Sky News and stuff like that. You, I mean, yeah, you couldn't trust politicians to bring this around - It wasn't a really proper education on what exactly they're going to do and what they're going to use.” (Australia, rural, in the discussion on SAI)

In such accounts, scientific knowledge is constructed as the antipode to populism and ideology. They also mirror slogans for listening to and

following the sciences, frequently heard in the climate movement, in marches and protests, and advanced by groups such as Scientist Rebellion (Karnik Hinks and Rödder, 2023). The below statements from the focus groups illustrate these two points:

“For example, the nuclear debate continues. In fact, the other party knows how bad nuclear is, but says yes to fill their pockets. [...] Let it be in a truly objective environment. Because there is something called scientific knowledge. There are truths. I expect it to be a discussion where these are taken as the route, the direction.” (Turkey, urban)

“I think this is because these conferences [COPs of the UNFCCC] do not include scientists that know about the consequences. We should listen to these people more than to state institutions that only think about growth and economy. Scientists should play a more important role.” (Germany rural, discussing governance of SAI)

4.3.2. Skepticism, disillusion and concerns

Corroborating our survey results on the high trust bestowed upon scientific institutions, only few focus group participants explicitly stated that they do not see a role for scientists in the governance of climate intervention technologies. Concerns about the partiality of and political influences on experts are however more common. Maintaining objectivity is thus seen as key to trustworthiness:

“Objectivity. That's key. They should be objective regardless of economic, social, or political interests.” (Spain, rural)

Honesty, transparency and balanced reporting of risks and benefits of the respective technologies assessed are brought forward as key criteria or conditions for trusting scientists. Skepticism towards scientists becomes apparent in some participants' reflections on how some experts are untrustworthy, biased or driven by interests, for example when funded by industry and commercial actors:

“Well, I expect them [scientists in the field] to do their job, but, you know, I think there's plenty of evidence to show that scientists that are funded from the private sector are encouraged to skew their data towards whoever's paying their bills. If they're generically funded through the government and the objective is for them to just do scientific research, give the actual truth and the actual answers, it needs to be independent funding. It cannot be funding based on any of the companies that are going to make these products, benefit from these products. It needs to be truly independent and that's why I keep going back to the government has to fund them.” (Australia, urban, in the decision on CDR in general)

“Well, they should be reliable, not falsify research results to accommodate the wishes of some interest group. It should be simply a scientific community, but it is also often the case that the scientific community is divided. Anyway, they should do their best to anticipate any positive or negative effects” (Poland, urban)

We also find frustrations among some - though comparatively few - participants that experts are not always listened to anyways. This reflects skepticism not about science per se but about policymaking and the actual basis of decision-making. We observe that the low trust in national governments identified in the survey can spill over to a sense of disillusion with decision-making more generally. Widely shared examples of the lack of evidence-based policymaking recur around the politics of climate change, particularly in the US:

“Because what we've seen, for example, in a country like America, if the governor, or whoever decides global warming does not exist, it doesn't matter what the science says, or whatever it decides, well, I'm the boss, and I decided in my term that global warming is not a problem, then they then pass on all these laws and everything that would undo what the previous one has done, just because this is the state that with the red or the blue.” (South Africa, urban)

Lastly, reflecting worries about potential implications and

applications of research on SRM methods, some participants express concerns about how conducting research on some methods would open the door to implementation, echoing the “slippery slope” argument also made by scholars on SRM (McLaren and Corry, 2021; Low et al., 2022b; Tang, 2023) and pointing more generally to researchers’ “responsibility to carefully consider the impact of statements and action” (Donner, 2017). In a few cases concerns among participants that researching novel technologies inevitably opens up avenues for implementation are also discussed for CDR, here exemplified by a participant’s concern over environmental impacts on Enhanced Rock Weathering:

“Moderator: What if scientists do research?”

Respondent: They’ll eventually do it, you’re destroying it [the fauna and flora].” (Spain rural, discussing Enhanced Rock Weathering)

5. Concluding discussion

Both qualitative and quantitative evidence from our study across 22 countries points to overall high levels of trust bestowed in scientific experts and institutions when it comes to the governance of climate intervention technologies. Transparency, independent funding sources, objectivity in assessing both risks and benefits, integrity and declaration of no competing interests are established by focus group participants as key features of trustworthy experts (see Fig. 3). With this trust placed in scientific experts and institutions also comes the responsibility to acknowledge and openly communicate uncertainties and unknowns. The - at times inflated - hopes of focus group participants that experts would be able to anticipate and eliminate all uncertainties around the side-effects of novel technologies such as SRM point to fundamental challenges related to communication about decision-making under uncertainty. Given the complex, post-normal nature of research into climate intervention technologies, there is need for wider discussion on the extent to which some uncertainties are fundamental – and how much is acceptable – when it comes to this topic.

Members of the public included in this study expect scientists to assume a variety of roles, with implications for how responsibilities and competences are allocated across the science-policy interface. In parts, citizens’ reflections on the role of experts in the governance of climate intervention technologies uphold the imaginary of linear science-policy relations and evidence-based policymaking. Scientific experts are frequently portrayed as impartial actors and honest brokers (Pielke, 2007) delivering objective facts and assessments of risks and side-effects. Here communication and knowledge dissemination appear as central expectations towards scientists.

At the same time, we find clear signs that publics do expect scientists working on climate intervention technologies to actively engage in public outreach and debate, advisory bodies and even decision-making. In over half of the countries - and often with analogies to (failures in) the management of the Covid-19 pandemic as well as in reaction to more general frustrations with vested interests in policymaking - a desire for experts to serve as outright decision authorities is expressed. These results echo reports about public preferences for delegating decision authority to experts on complex environmental issues such as carbon emissions and climate change, previously found in experimental studies in 7 European countries (Bertsou, 2022). Also, with regard to CDR, similar observations on public preferences for expert-led decisions were made in German focus groups on ecosystem restoration (Kuhn et al., 2024). The underlying rationale, and the extent to which these preferences for expert authority mirror distrust and skepticism towards political elites, deserve further attention. Our results point at least tentatively to important interactions between technocratic tolerance and low trust in governmental actors (Bertsou and Pastorella, 2016) – dynamics that politicians in some of the European representative democracies with particularly low levels of trust such as Germany, Austria or Poland should attend to.

We do not find evidence in the set of focus groups suggesting that active societal engagement of scientists in the field of climate intervention technologies would be perceived to harm their credibility or trustworthiness - corroborating findings by Cologna et al. (2021) on

Fig. 3. Conceptual representation of key elements in public perceptions of experts in the governance of climate intervention technologies, including types of expertise, roles and ingredients for trustworthiness. Note: Distribution in the inner circle qualitatively reflects the unequal shares of mentions of social sciences as relevant expertise in the focus groups. The visualization does not imply strong relations or any directionality between elements across the three circles.

perceptions of and expectations towards climate scientists in the US and Germany. The democratic implications of technocratic practices, redistributing decision-making power from elected representatives to appointed experts, are little problematized by publics in the focus groups. This includes those with participants in countries with different systems of government – whether other types of democracies or less democratic regimes, corroborating [Bertsou and Caramani's \(2020\)](#) observation of perceived “technocratic legitimacy”. Given the limited time in our focus groups, this aspect, however, deserves attention in future research.

Finally, our findings underscore the importance of a better integration of diverse types of disciplinary as well as practical knowledge in public conversations around climate intervention technologies. The (almost) absence of social scientists featuring in publics' reflections in the focus groups on the relevant experts for governing CDR and SRM might to some degree mirror the underrepresentation of social sciences in funding of climate research ([Overland and Sovacool, 2020](#)) and of CDR methods ([Müller-Hansen et al., under review](#)), even if there is in the focus groups an implicit demand for such expertise in relation to multidimensional assessments, and interdisciplinary collaborations. This disbalance deserves greater attention considering that decisions around CDR and SRM are not merely questions of a technical nature but ones that are deeply political, legal, economic, and ethical, with potentially wide-ranging societal impacts. This observation also tasks social scientists to become more involved and intensify their efforts to actively communicate and engage in public and policy debates and make their knowledge and expertise better available to a larger audience. Working towards a more pluralistic knowledge base for tackling the wicked conundrums in governing climate intervention technologies also requires providing space for non-scientific expertise to be heard. Publics' mentions of practical and experienced-based expertise for approaches like afforestation and soil carbon sequestration speak to the importance of transdisciplinary engagement of farmers, rural and indigenous communities in planning the deployment of CDR.

Ethical Review Statement

This research was approved by the Institutional Review Board at Aarhus University 2021-13. Full and informed consent was given by all participants before the beginning of the study, along with all participants being notified about the fact that their data would be handled in a fully anonymous manner and in complete accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation and any other pertinent data-security regulations, that any data would be analyzed in an aggregate fashion and would not be personally identifiable in any way, and that they had the right to withdraw their participation at any time.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Livia Fritz: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lucilla Losi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Chad M. Baum:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Data curation. **Sean Low:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Benjamin K. Sovacool:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104005).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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